

HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF URBAN TRADITIONS AND CULTURAL LAYERS IN THE AXSIKENT ARCHAEOLOGICAL COMPLEX.

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes the history of urban planning of the archaeological site of Akhsikent, the stages of formation of cultural layers, and the characteristics of the socio-economic development of the city based on archaeological finds. The research highlights the place of Akhsikent in the history of urbanization of Central Asia based on the results of archaeological excavations, written sources, and modern scientific literature. The development of the ark, shahristan, and rabod parts of the city, as well as samples of material culture, are also scientifically evaluated [1; 2].*

***Keywords:** Akhsikent, cultural heritage, Open-air museum, museumization works, Akhsikent archaeological park, archeology, urban planning, cultural layer, shahristan, ark, rabod, urbanization, material culture, Fergana Valley.*

ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОРОДСКИХ ТРАДИЦИЙ И КУЛЬТУРНЫХ ЯРУСОВ В АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКОМ КОМПЛЕКСЕ АКСИКЕНТ.

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Аннотация: В данной статье на основе археологических находок анализируется история градостроительства археологического памятника Ахсикент, этапы формирования культурных слоев и особенности социально-экономического развития города. Исследование освещает место Ахсикента в истории урбанизации Центральной Азии на основе результатов археологических раскопок, письменных источников и современной научной литературы. Научно оценивается также развитие частей города, относящихся к ковчегу, шахристану и рабоду, а также образцы материальной культуры [1; 2].

Ключевые слова: Ахсикент, культурное наследие, музей под открытым небом, музейные работы, археологический парк Ахсикента, археология, градостроительство, культурный слой, Шахристан, ковчег, рабод, урбанизация, материальная культура, Ферганская долина.

AXSIKENT ARXEOLGIK MAJMUASIDA SHAHARSOZLIK AN’ANALARI VA MADANIY QATLAMLARNING TARIXIY TAHLILI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Axsikent arxeologik yodgorligining shaharsozlik tarixi, madaniy qatlamlarning shakllanish bosqichlari hamda arxeologik topilmalar asosida shaharning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlanish xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida arxeologik qazishmalar natijalari, yozma manbalar va zamonaviy ilmiy adabiyotlar asosida Axsikentning Markaziy Osiyo urbanizatsiyasi tarixidagi o‘rni yoritiladi. Shuningdek, shaharning ark, shahriston va rabod qismlarining rivojlanishi hamda moddiy madaniyat namunalari ilmiy jihatdan baholanadi [1; 2].

***Kalit so‘zlar:** Axsikent, madaniy meros, Ochiq osmon ostidagi muzey, muzeylashtrish ishlari, Axsikent arxeologiya parki, arxeologiya, shaharsozlik, madaniy qatlam, shahriston, ark, rabod, urbanizatsiya, moddiy madaniyat, Farg‘ona vodiysi.*

Introduction

Among the ancient cities of Uzbekistan, Akhsikent occupies a special place with its centuries-old history and high cultural heritage. This city, one of the political and economic centers of the Fergana Valley, has long developed as one of the important points of the Great Silk Road [3].

Archaeological research conducted in recent years has yielded important scientific results in determining the stages of urban development of Akhsikent. In particular, stratigraphic analysis of cultural layers allows reconstructing different periods of the city's history [1.19]. Formation of Akhsikent and urban development According to archaeological data, the first cultural layers of Akhsikent date back to the 3rd–2nd centuries BC [2.38]. The city is located in a favorable geographical area, which allowed for the development of irrigated agriculture and trade. By the Middle Ages, Akhsikent had formed as the largest city in Fergana. The city consisted of three main parts: In the 3rd century BC, on the site of the Akhsikent monument, the city of Fergana (Akhsikat), the capital of the ancient Fergana state, was founded on an area of more than 40 hectares. From a topographic point of view, it consisted of 3 parts: a fortress (ark), an inner city (shahristan) and a city

(rabod). By the 2nd century BC, a settlement of craftsmen - a rabad - appeared outside the shahristan on an area of about 10 hectares. The fortress of the city and the shahristan were surrounded by defensive walls made of pakhsa and raw bricks, more than 3

meters thick. Ark - the administrative center; Shahrستان - the main residential area; Rabod - the outer part where craftsmen and merchants lived. The fact that the city was built in this state indicates that Akhsikent had developed urban planning traditions.

Stratigraphic analysis of cultural layers.

Archaeological excavations have revealed cultural layers several meters thick in Akhsikent. These layers confirm that the city was a center of continuous settlement for a long time [2.40]. Pottery from the early antiquity period, remains of farm structures and defense walls were found in the lower layers. In the upper layers, houses, baths and production workshops of the IX-XII centuries were found [2.37].

The study of cultural layers makes it possible to determine the stages of economic and demographic development of the city.

Archaeological findings and their historical significance

The samples of material culture found in Akhsikent show the high level of development of the city. Finds include: glazed pottery; metal weapons, smithy products; coins; jewelry; there are glass containers [1.48]. In particular, metallurgical finds indicate that Akhsikent was one of the largest iron-producing centers in Central Asia [2.42]. Most of the craftsmen were engaged in the production of iron and steel and the manufacture of various objects and weapons from them. Archaeological research has made it possible to determine the economic potential of the city of Fergana-Akhsikant and its place in Central Asia. It is known that the master craftsmen of Akhsikant knew how to obtain pure steel ("bulat") from enriched iron. To do this, they placed the enriched iron raw material in a special cylindrical container ("crucible") made of kaolin clay, added charcoal

and other additives unknown to us, and then placed it in a special furnace. The inside of the furnace was also plastered with kaolin clay. A special vessel (crucible) and furnace made of kaolin clay were used to withstand temperatures of 1650-1700o C. The technology of steel production was kept secret. The finished steel was cooled in a vessel and then obtained by

breaking the vessel. The price of swords made of such steel was very high. Therefore, such weapons were often made on orders from wealthy people or merchants. made. The weapons made in Akhsikat were famous all over the world under the name of "Damascus" swords. We can also learn this from the information in the sources. For example, in the sources written by the Arab historians-geographers Al Muqaddasi and Ibn Hawqal, it is said that when the Ustrushana iron fell into the hands of the masters of Fergana (Akhsikat), it was transformed into things (weapons) that exceed the human mind. These weapons were of two types, one was made of hard steel, similar to Indian steel, and the other was made of soft steel. Numismatic materials are an important source for shedding light on the city's economic ties with Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, and the countries of the East.

The role of Akhsikent urbanization in the history of Central Asia

The urban planning system of Akhsikent has common features with such large centers as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Uzbek. However, the city's specialization in metallurgy and crafts is its distinctive feature [4.24].

Since 2019, a concept for the development of Akhsikent as an "open-air museum" has been developed, and comprehensive work has begun on this basis.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's visit to the Akhsikent monument on February 28, 2019 and the "Akhsikent Archaeological Park" being created based on this [1.4] Uzbekistan has set new tasks for the science of archaeology. According to the project of the Turkish architect Guray Kaymak, the territory is divided into functional zones: exhibition areas, tourist corridors, observation platforms, and based on his project, museumization work is being carried out at an accelerated pace.

The periodic study of the cultural layers of the Akhsikent monument, the exhibitions of the “Open-air Museum” organized on the monument, and the exhibits placed in the “Archaeological Museum” to be built are of great importance in the history of our statehood.

The structures identified as a result of archaeological research indicate that the city had a centralized management system and a developed communal infrastructure. This confirms that Akhsikent played an important role in the history of statehood in the Fergana Valley [6-43].

Summary

The Aksikent archaeological complex is an important source for the study of the history of urbanization and statehood of the Fergana Valley. Cultural layers and archaeological findings make it possible to restore the centuries-old stages of the city's development. The urban planning system, craft centers and examples of material culture show that Akhsikent was one of the major political and economic centers of Central Asia. It should be noted that in its time it was considered one of the largest capital cities not only in Central Asia, but also in the entire region. The wide-scale research conducted by historians and archeologists and Turkish architects at the Ahsikent monument, the construction of an open-air museum will provide more information about the history of our country, create a new tourist route in the region, and most importantly, will serve as an important contribution to the illumination of the rich history of the nation.

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